

CEDEFOP

European Centre for the Development
of Vocational Training

Approaches and tools for comparing and recognising VET qualifications

Insights from Cedefop's research

Overview

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Introduction

- The EU's working-age population is projected to **decline by 57.4 million by 2100** (European Commission, 2023)
- **24 million individuals** aged 20-64 have an unmet need for employment (Eurostat, 2024)
- Rise in regulated professions from 5,400 (2016) to **5,700 (2023)** (European Court of Auditors, 2024).
- Comparing and recognising can:
 - **Identify differences and similarities** to recognise qualifications and skills across institutions and borders.
 - **Facilitate access** to employment and learning opportunities.
- 'Formal recognition of learning outcomes' (European Council, 2017)

Multiple challenges

EU policy background

*...from mutual recognition to comparability and transparency...
...from inputs to learning outcomes...*

Cedefop's contribution

2009

POLICIES AND PRACTICES
IN EUROPE

2016

A COMPARATIVE STUDY

2018

Analysis and overview
of NQF level descriptors
in European countries

2020

2022

Towards methodologies for analysing
and comparing learning outcomes

2024

Research paper
Transparency and
transferability of
learning outcomes:
a 20-year journey

Analysis of developments at
European and national level

Main objectives and methods of the study

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How have existing EU transparency tools facilitated the process of comparing and recognising VET qualifications in Europe, and what opportunities exist for their enhancement?
2. How do national authorities and stakeholders across Europe currently compare and recognise VET qualifications?
3. What common themes and concepts can be identified that could help develop a practically oriented framework for comparing and recognising VET qualifications for diverse purposes in Europe?

Main objectives and methods of the study

STUDY'S SCOPE

foreign qualifications defined as part of each country's VET, incl. post-secondary and higher VET qualifications.

DATA ANALYSIS

- Mapping and analysis of existing EU transparency tools regarding recognition
- ReferNet survey (27 countries responded)
- In-depth expert interviews (N=22)
- Existing knowledge within CEDEFOP supported the analysis

Main themes

1. Availability of and access to information on qualifications, learning outcomes and recognition procedures
2. Processing of information regarding comparison and recognition
3. Diverse recognition practices
4. Addressing mutual trust through political cooperation and framework building
5. Future-proofing via systematic learning from and between Member States, existing tools, available research and piloting

1. Availability of and access to information on qualifications, learning outcomes and recognition procedures

Main challenges

- Information is dispersed, (the '**silo logic**'), not always up to date or digitally available.
- **No comprehensive entry points** for information on qualifications, learning outcomes and recognition at national and European levels.
- Information is **complex and using special terms**.
- Information is **rigid and not adapted** to individual's specific needs before, during and after comparison and recognition process.
- **Language barriers**.

Priority solutions

- Develop **digital and comprehensive entry point** for information on qualifications and credentials (all levels and types).
- **Use standardised, short descriptions** to express learning outcomes.
- **Streamline and simplify** recognition processes and provide clear information on these.
- After recognition, provide information for the individual concerning **rights and next steps** if qualification has not fully been recognised.
- Information available at least **in English** (on top of national languages).

2. Processing of information regarding comparison and recognition

Main challenges

- EU transparency tools and legal texts **employ similar terms** to describe different concepts and concepts are **not consistently applied**.
- Development of new initiatives tends to **overlook accumulated experience**.
- **Lack of knowledge and understanding** of existing transparency tools amongst stakeholders and individuals.
- Implementation of AI/digital tools may take place without a **careful consideration of the characteristics of learning and qualifications**.

European and national tools

In all countries, the following tools are utilised

Professional Qualifications Directive

All countries use for regulated professions.

NQF

- Often employed for identifying the level
- Use of national NQF descriptors for comparison less common
- Increasing importance of qualification-specific LOs

EQF

- A tool to define the level of (foreign) qualification
- Referencing of the NQFs to the EQF is a requirement

EQF and NQF are the primary tools for supporting comparison (level)

Other European tools used by countries:

ESCO

- Mentioned in connection with EURES, Europass, national databases, qualification standards
- **Divided views on its potential** as a comparison tool with conditions (e.g. AI-supported matching tools) or too detailed and/or not fitting into national systems; also potential is seen

Europass

- **Diploma Supplement** and **Certificate Supplement** considered useful
- Overall considered as useful digital tool for obtaining information on qualifications

Lisbon Recognition Convention (LRC)

- All countries have ratified the LRC and **use it in connection with HE**
- Some countries **apply its principles to VET**

Recommendation on Automatic Recognition

- Mentioned in many responses, mostly in **connection with HE**

European Learning Model (ELM)

- Countries have only recently started mapping exercises or implementation
- Some countries report on **its potential** for comparing qualifications

The role of learning outcomes

- Frequent reference to curricula, programmes and learning outcomes
- Learning outcomes are used to define the NQF level of qualifications
- **Balance occupation-specific (professional) skills/ general subjects / and transversal skills not visible** → Most attention on occupation-specific skills

PERSISTING BARRIERS

- Differences in quality and granularity of descriptors;
- Generality of learning outcomes (sometimes seen as abstract);
- Translation issues;
- Comparison of the content/learning outcomes is considered labour-intensive.

Priority solutions

- Initiate co-operation between Member States on the use of AI language models, **building on the conceptual specifics of qualifications and learning outcomes.**
- Conceptual clarification and implementation of AI language models need to **evolve according to accumulated experience.**
- Critical look on digital transparency tools from the **perspective of the needs of individual learners and employees.**
- Intensify co-operation between Member States to **develop consistent and comprehensive use of** existing comparison and recognition tools.

3. Diverse recognition practices

Main challenges

- **Rigidity in assessing** foreign VET qualifications.
- Recognition practices sometimes implicitly used for **protecting sector or other interests**.
- **(Too) many criteria** being used.
- **Learning outcomes are not presented** in a way that they could be used as a basis for recognition.
- **Learning outcomes are not fully understood** by those making decisions.
- **Many approaches and actors in one country**, which may lead to difficulties in coordinating the work and confuse individuals.

Recognition practices: How do countries compare?

- **Purpose of comparison:** further study, labour market, divided into regulated and non-regulated professions
- **Case-by-case analysis**
- **Automatic recognition appears to be rare - exceptions** under the PQD or bi-/multilateral government agreements
- **National qualification and/or professional standards (occupations)** are used as benchmarks
- **Sometimes through supported assessment** (e.g. expert commissions/panels)
- **Additional requirements** may be requested

Criteria for comparison/recognition of qualifications

Context-related

- Legal basis
- Qualification system in the country of origin
- Place of the qualification in the qualification system
- Authenticity of documents

Quality-related

- Status of the institution
- Independent external evaluation of the training or institution

Qualification-related

- Status/title
- NQF/EQF level
- Formal rights
- Duration
- Credits
- Subjects, structure, practical training
- Learning outcomes

Concept of ‘substantial difference’

- Well known-concept, but little information on what it implies in practice
- Some countries use the UNESCO Global Recognition Convention definition
- ‘Limits’ mentioned related to: content, duration, need for equivalency exams

Priority solutions

- More aligned and transparent approaches for comparison and recognition **balancing the need for gatekeeping with interests of learners.**
- Critical look at the **number of actors.**
- **European co-operation and network** for exchanging information and agreeing on key criteria and good practice for recognition of VET qualifications.
- **Strengthen common understanding** about the concept of substantial difference.

4. Addressing mutual trust through political co-operation and framework building

Main challenges

- On EU and national levels, longstanding practice has been to focus on individual sectors/levels of education rather than **considering the qualification system as a whole ('silo-thinking')**.
- Unclear what kind of information and/or measures are needed to **add to trust between countries**.
- Insufficient information and **transparency in quality assurance procedures** in Member States.

Priority solutions

- Intensify efforts to find ways to **add to mutual trust between qualifications systems**, all levels and types of qualifications.
- Considering **qualification system as a whole** with a view of lifelong learning when updating old or developing new initiatives for comparison and recognition.
- Making sure information concerning qualifications and learning outcomes is **relevant, transparent and up-to-date**.
- Making information on **quality assurance** available.

5. Future-proofing via systematic learning from and between Member States, existing tools, available research and piloting

Main challenges

- **Not much information available** on recognition decisions or comparability statements and their underlying rationale at national or stakeholder levels.
- **No established co-operation** structures for the recognition of foreign VET qualifications.
- **Very little follow-up** concerning the impact of recognition for individuals.
- **No coherent mechanism for providing information** about recognition for different purposes in Member States.

Monitoring and follow up

- **Statistics** are available (e.g. about the implementation of the PQD)
- **Annual monitoring reports** about recognition activities, reports on e.g. numbers of applicants, handling times, qualifications, awarding countries.
- **User surveys** about the customer satisfaction.
- Only few countries have made surveys about **the effect/impact** of the comparison/recognition for the applicant and/or the employer.

Priority solutions

- **Organising mutual learning** to identify good practice in the recognition of foreign VET qualifications.
- **Analysis of benefits of bilateral or regional agreements** and associated qualifications as well as reasons for their success.
- **Systematically gather and analyse** the outcomes of research, pilot projects (for example Erasmus+) and evaluations (“looking back to look ahead”) and use those results for further developing recognition practice.

Concluding remarks

- **EU transparency tools** have been instrumental but lack full coherence and visibility.
- **Learning outcomes** are crucial for recognition processes, but the specifics of how and under which conditions this can be achieved require further research.
- **Digitalisation and AI** can enhance the efficiency and accessibility of transparency tools but require a systematic approach and conceptual clarity.
- **Achieving conceptual clarity** is crucial to ensure consistency and transparency.
- **Building mutual trust** between national qualification systems and for different types of qualifications is essential.

Taking work further

Cedefop working paper

‘Policies and tools for comparing and recognising VET qualifications – An overview’

Follow-up project 2026 – 2028

‘From comparing to recognising VET qualifications: Towards a practice-oriented methodology’, with 3 thematic areas:

- Approaches and criteria for comparing and recognising VET qualifications for learning and work;
- The use of digitalisation and transparency tools to support comparison and recognition of VET qualifications;
- Recognising foreign VET qualifications for the purpose of employment.

Thank you

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Project page:

Comparison and recognition of learning outcomes:

www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/projects/comparing-vet-qualifications

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